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IDENTIFYING PROSPECTIVE TRENDS IN NON-COMPLIANCE WITH ADVERTISING LEGISLATION

Victoriia Shvedun

Doctor of Science (Public Administration), Full Professor,
WYŻSZA SZKOŁA KADR MENEDŻERSKICH, Konin, Poland

ORCID: 0000-0002-5170-4222

Oleksandr Kurnosov

PhD in Public Administration, Purchasing Executive,
Group of Companies OLKO

ORCID: 0000-0003-4180-4788

Abstract. The authors identify the prospective trends in non-compliance with advertising legislation based on the assessment of average retrospective trends in the presence of violations of advertising legislation in the world. The authors think that intuitive and formalized forecasting methods are similar in composition to expert and factographic methods. In particular, the first ones are based on information about the current and past development trends of the research object, which is actually available. The results of the forecasting the of the prospective quantity of non-compliance with advertising legislation shows a steady tendency to increase. Accordingly, correction of a similar situation is possible only by assessing the effectiveness of state regulation of non-compliance with advertising legislation through the development of effective technologies for the state's response to facts of non-compliance with advertising legislation.

Keywords: advertising, forecasting method, television and radio organizations, advertising legislation, violations, state authorities.

Introduction. Today's advertising campaign helps aspiring entrepreneurs to make themselves known, and big businesses to remain relevant. According to statistics, about 60% of users search for information about goods and services on the Internet. It is clear that these are potential buyers of goods or services and the main task is to convey information about the company to the target audience. However, violations of advertising legislation remain a very significant problem.

Literature review

The author of the work (Evans, David S., 2009) claims that online advertising accounts for almost 9% of all advertising in the United States. That share is expected to increase as more media is consumed online as more advertisers shift spending to online technology. Expanding online advertising transforms the advertising business by providing better methods for matching advertisers and consumers and transforming the media business by providing a source of revenue for online media firms that compete with traditional media firms. The sharp decline in the newspaper industry is one manifestation of the symbiotic relationship between online content and advertising. Online advertising is provided by a number of interconnected multisystem platforms that facilitate the selection of advertisers and consumers. These intermediaries are increasingly using detailed individual data, forecasting methods and matching algorithms to create more effective matches between consumers and advertisements.

This review (John Ford, Varsha Jain, Ketan Wadhvani & Damini Goyal Gupta, 2023) aims to chart the evolution of the field by conducting a bibliometric and framework analysis of 75 advertising articles on artificial intelligence published between 1990 and 2022. Key findings of the study are publishing trends in artificial intelligence advertising, as well as research contexts identified through bibliographic

linkage. Four topics have become key areas of artificial intelligence advertising research: software advertising and automation, ad planning and engagement, ad efficiency, and trust in artificial intelligence advertising. In addition, this review offers practical recommendations and future lines of research for the development of advertising literature on artificial intelligence. Finally, the review offers broader results for industry and academia, highlighting how the topics identified can inform advertising practice and contribute to the theoretical development of the given field.

The work (G. Douglas Olsen, John W. Pracejus, 2020) is the first relatively experimental study of individual advertising, where people customize specific elements of a message, in some cases in perceived collaboration with others, varying the level of ad customization. The authors believe that as personalization increases, the strength of a customer's perceived relationship with the company, a sense of engagement with the task, a perception of the trust and integrity of the company, and attitudes toward advertising demonstrate that when overlay is large, individual ads outperform the random version or even expand this in the context of social media, where participants believe they are socially co-creating ads with others.

The study (Alsharif, A.H., Salleh, N.Z.M., Alrawad, M. et al., 2023) looks at the effectiveness of advertising calls in stimulating engagement and action on and outside social media platforms. In the experiment, positive, negative and coercive ads were distributed on social media and promoted throughout the week. Three advertisements were monitored in an A/B test experiment to provide an applicable comparison. The metrics used included screenings, likes, promotions and clicks according to the concept of interacting with multiple actors on social media. The data was extracted using Facebook's ad manager and website data. Significance was tested with a series of chi-square tests. The ads reached more than 21,000 users. A significant effect was found for the type of appeal for engagement and behavioural

actions. The findings support the use of negative advertising calls compared to positive and collaborative calls.

The results of the literature review on advertising topics allow us to conclude that the articles are mainly focused on separate areas of advertising activity.

In view of the above relevance of the topic of this study, the purpose of the article is to identify the specifics of reengineering of business processes of the provision of public services, as well as to study of the problems and prospects of these processes' realization.

However, there are no forecasts of public administration in the field of advertising in the scientific literature. Based on this, it is proposed to carry out forecasting in the current work regarding the prospective quantity of non-compliance with advertising legislation. The specified forecasting is proposed to be performed on the basis of the specified method and model. For this, it is necessary to consider the essence of the relevant definitions.

Accordingly, the purpose of the work is identifying prospective trends in non-compliance with advertising legislation based on the assessment of average retrospective trends in the presence of violations of advertising legislation in the world.

Methodology

In the work, the use of the trend extrapolation method, which belongs to the group of formalized extrapolation forecasting methods, is proposed for forecasting the prospective quantity of non-compliance with advertising legislation.

Dynamic (time) series serve as the basis for building forecasts using extrapolation formalized methods. In the general case, a dynamic series is a series of inspections conducted regularly at the same time intervals. As such a time interval, it is proposed to take a year. In accordance, average statistical reporting on non-

compliance with advertising legislation by national television and radio organizations during is the necessary initial data for constructing a dynamic range forecast.

Main part

A forecasting method is traditionally understood as a sequence of actions that must be implemented to obtain a forecast model.

In turn, the predictive model is an adequate functional description of the process or phenomenon to be investigated, with the aim of obtaining values reflecting its prospective state [2; 10].

According to the degree of formalization, forecasting methods are divided into intuitive and formalized (deterministic) ones. In particular, it is advisable to use intuitive forecasting methods in situations where it is not possible to take into account the influence of numerous factors on the object of forecasting due to its significant complexity or the impossibility of description using mathematical tools. Under such conditions, various expert evaluations are traditionally used.

Formalized forecasting methods make it possible to form a mathematical dependence that can serve as a forecasting model, which makes it possible to calculate future values of the state of the object under investigation [10; 14].

The classification of forecasting methods is described in more detail in Table 1 [2; 10; 14].

Table 1

Generalized classification of forecasting methods

The name of the group of forecasting methods	The name of the subgroup of forecasting methods	Types of forecasting methods
Intuitive	Individual expert assessments	Interview, analytical method, building scenarios, generating ideas
	Collective expert evaluations	Committee method, collective generation of ideas ("brainstorming"), Delphi method, matrix method, heuristic method
Formalized (deterministic)	Predictive extrapolation	Trend extrapolation, regression analysis, exponential smoothing, moving average method, adaptive smoothing, autoregressive transformation, harmonic weighting method
	Modeling methods	Structural modeling, network modeling, matrix modeling, simulation modeling

Source: compiled independently according to []

In particular, within the limits of using the interview method, which belongs to the subgroup of individual expert evaluations in the group of intuitive methods of forecasting, direct contact between an expert and a specialist is carried out according to the "question-answer" scheme. When using the analytical method, any predicted situation is analyzed from a logical point of view, based on the results of which appropriate analytical reports are compiled. The method of building scenarios is

based on the definition of the features of the logic of the realization of the object being studied over time, under different conditions [2; 5].

Intuitive methods of forecasting, implying the use of collective expert evaluations, make it possible to obtain more accurate results than in the process of processing individual judgments of experts.

A special place among intuitive forecasting methods is occupied by the heuristic method, the essence of which is the construction and further truncation of the "search tree" of expert assessments. At the same time, expert evaluations obtained through a systematic survey of highly qualified specialists are a subject to specialized processing. This method is traditionally used to construct forecasts corresponding to the solution of problems of a scientific and technical nature, the specifics of the development of which cannot be fully or partially formalized [3; 10].

Quite often in practice, combined methods including several ones of the above mentioned are used. Most often, a combination of expert evaluations with other methods is used.

In general, intuitive and formalized forecasting methods are similar in composition to expert and factographic methods. In particular, the first ones are based on information about the current and past development trends of the research object, which is actually available. Accordingly, expert methods are based on information obtained from the results of expert evaluation of the research object.

At the same time, it should be taken into account that the construction of any forecast involves the presence of three consecutive stages.

The first stage is research. The key task of this stage is to determine the probable results of the prospective development of the research object and to make a choice from a set of options for one or more positive results. In fact, this stage provides an opportunity to reveal a wide range of prospects, which have the form of

one problem of a scientific and technical nature or a number of them, which can be solved within the forecast period [7; 14].

The second stage of forecast construction is programmatic. It consists in determining possible ways of achieving results that are expected and necessary. In addition, at this stage, the time period necessary for the implementation of each of the possible options is determined, as well as the degree of reliability of successfully achieving the specified result according to this or that option is established.

The third stage of forecasting is organizational. It is traditionally presented in the form of a set of measures of an organizational and technical nature, which ensure the achievement of a certain result by one or another option. At this stage, the essential aspects are the availability of resources and accumulated scientific and technical potential. At this stage, it is necessary to formulate a hypothesis based on a scientific point of view for the prospective development of the research object. At the same time, a probabilistic assessment of resource distribution, as well as the future state of the research object, should be provided.

To analyze the trend based on dynamic series and to build the necessary forecast taking into account the regularities present in the time series, the trend equation is traditionally used, which is most often chosen in cases of stochastic dependencies, in which all influencing factors cannot be taken into account.

The trend reflects the averaged values of changes in the state of the research object over time. At the same time, it is assumed that the influence of all the main factors can be expressed in the time factor. Despite the fact that time cannot be a mechanism for the manifestation of trends and regularities, it is assumed that it accumulates the action of all influential factors and expresses it in the form of a trend equation.

The choice of the type of trend equation is based on the analysis of the degree

of quality of its reflection of the regularity of the existing trend. The criterion of this quality should be considered the value of the reliability of the approximation – the coefficient of determination R^2 , which demonstrates the degree of compliance of the trend equation with the original data. The closer R^2 is to 1, the more reliably the model describes the real situation [2; 10; 14].

Accordingly, the selection of the trend equation was carried out by analyzing the calculated coefficients of determination for its various types based on the retrospective dynamic series. Table 2 shows the results of selecting the type of trend equation [1; 15; 16].

Table 2

The results of selecting the type of trend equation

Type of trend equation	Functional display	The value of the coefficient of determination R^2
Linear	$y = 4,8 \times x - 9613$	0.12
Logarithmic	$y = 9641,2 \times \ln(x) - 73295$	0.12
Polynomial (second degree)	$y = 9,7143 \times x^2 - 39047 \times x + 39237053,29$	0.82

Accordingly, among all the values of the coefficient of determination presented in Table 2, the closest to 1 is the value corresponding to the polynomial trend of the second degree. Accordingly, it is advisable to continue the search for the most optimal line of the polynomial trend, increasing its degree (Table 3) [1; 15; 16].

Table 3

Results of selecting the power of the polynomial trend

The degree of the polynomial trend equation	Functional display	The value of the coefficient of determination R^2
Second	$y = 9,7143 \times x^2 - 39047 \times x + 39237053,29$	0.82
Third	$y = 1,5833 \times x^3 - 9537,8 \times x^2 + 19151422,99 \times x - 12818370376,21$	0.84
Fourth	$y = 6,0417 \times x^4 - 4857 \times x^3 + 146444060,46 \times x^2 - 196228598518,05 \times x + 98601621926645,7$	1

It can be seen from Table 3 that the optimal value of the coefficient of determination corresponds to the fourth power of the polynomial equation of the trend. Accordingly, it can be taken as a basis for building a forecast of the prospective quantity of violations of advertising legislation. The forecasting results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4

Forecast on the number of violations of advertising legislation by national television and radio organizations during 2013-2018

Year	The number of violations of advertising legislation
2024	49
2025	54
2026	59
2027	63
2028	68
2029	73

As can be seen from the forecasting results, the prospective number of non-compliance with advertising legislation shows a steady tendency to increase.

Accordingly, correction of a similar situation is possible only by assessing the effectiveness of state regulation of non-compliance with advertising legislation through the development of effective technologies for the state's response to facts of non-compliance with advertising legislation.

Conclusions

If violations of the legislation in the field of advertising are detected, it is recommended to make a decision on the imposition of penalties, which should be issued in 2 copies, where one sample remains with the competent person, and the other – with the advertising subject.

Legal analysis of the situation with non-compliance with advertising legislation determines that penalties can be imposed on both advertising manufacturers and their distributors and advertisers themselves.

The analysis of documents determines that in order to start a case on violation of advertising legislation, it will be necessary to draw up an appropriate protocol, which will be the basis for starting work on the case.

Such a protocol should be drawn up by officials of the competent authorities above, namely the decision on imposing penalties.

The mechanism of consideration of the case provides that the competent person must start the case within three days from the moment of registration of the protocol.

After that, it is necessary to inform the subject of advertising (potential offender) about the consideration of such a case (by mail or through electronic means of communication or in person).

Discussion

Every year the number of advertising is growing, more and more of its forms and types appear, it has become part of the daily life of a modern person. It seems

impossible to live a week, an hour or even a minute without meeting the ad. Any goods, products of the service need active promotion due to huge competition. Current statutes governing relations in the field of advertising, quite in detail and clearly establish the rights of participants of such relations, their responsibility for any violations, as well as requirements for the parties. However, the constant increase in advertising volumes entails an increasing complication of the norms related to the emergence, development and termination of various legal relations in the field of advertising, therefore so important is the prompt and timely update and improvement of regulatory documents, concerning this sphere.

References

1. Advertising – Worldwide. URL: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/amo/advertising/worldwide> (accessed: 04.02.2022).
2. Albright, R.E. What can past technology forecasts tell us about the future? *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 2002, 69, 443–464.
3. Alsharif, A.H., Salleh, N.Z.M., Alrawad, M. et al. Exploring global trends and future directions in advertising research: A focus on consumer behavior. *Curr Psychol* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-04812-w>
4. Bell, R., Mieth, L. & Buchner, A. Coping with high advertising exposure: a source-monitoring perspective. *Cogn. Research* 7, 82 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41235-022-00433-2>.
5. Castle, J.L.; Hendry, D.F.; Martinez, A.B. Evaluating Forecasts, Narratives and Policy Using a Test of Invariance. *Econometrics* 2017, 5, 39.
6. G. Douglas Olsen, John W. Pracejus, Customized advertising: Allowing consumers to directly tailor messages leads to better outcomes for the brand, *Journal*

of Business Research, Volume 116, 2020, Pages 245-257, ISSN 0148-2963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.04.054>.

7. Evans, David S. 2009. "The Online Advertising Industry: Economics, Evolution, and Privacy." *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 23 (3): 37-60.

8. Fotios Petropoulos, Daniele Apiletti, Vassilios Assimakopoulos, Mohamed Zied, et al. Forecasting: theory and practice, *International Journal of Forecasting*, Volume 38, Issue 3, 2022, Pages 705-871, ISSN 0169-2070, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2021.11.001>.

9. John Ford, Varsha Jain, Ketan Wadhvani, Damini Goyal Gupta, AI advertising: An overview and guidelines, *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 166, 2023, 114124, ISSN 0148-2963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.114124>.

10. Makridakis, S.; Hyndman, R.J.; Petropoulos, F. Forecasting in social settings: The state of the art. *Int. J. Forecast.* 2019, 36, 15–28.

11. Saleem S., & Abideen Z. (2011). Effective advertising and its influence on consumer buying behaviour. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(3), 55–67.

12. Silberstein, R. B., & Nield, G. E. (2012). Measuring emotion in advertising research: Prefrontal brain activity. *IEEE Pulse*, 3(3), 24–27.

13. Stanton, S., Armstrong, W., & Huettel, S. (2017). Neuromarketing: Ethical implications of its use and potential misuse. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 144(4), 799–811. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3059-0>.

14. Twenge, J. M., Martin, G. N., & Spitzberg, B. H. (2019). Trends in U.S. adolescents' media use, 1976–2016: The rise of digital media, the decline of TV, and the (near) demise of print. *Psychology of Popular Media Culture*, 8(4), 329–345.

15. 130 advertising statistics: trends, automation, and marketing strategies. URL: <https://www.linearity.io/blog/advertising-statistics/> (accessed: 04.02.2024).

16. 142 Notable Advertising Statistics: 2024 Market Analysis & Data. URL: <https://financesonline.com/advertising-statistics/> (accessed: 04.02.2024).